

COMPUTER APPLICATION IN BUSINESS

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Unit-1

- 1. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY BASICS**
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- 4. NEED FOR INFORMATION**
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1.1 Information Technology Basics

- **Data:** The word Data is used to refer to a fact or facts about the person, place, object, event or concept. It can be considered as the raw material of information.
- **Information:** Information is a processed data, placed into a meaningful context for the recipient. Information presents a picture of reality to a user.
- **System:** A system is a group of interrelated components working together towards a common goal by accepting inputs and producing outputs in an organised transaction process. It is a group of interrelated or interacting elements of forming a unified

1.2. Information Definition

- Information systems (IS) are the study of complementary networks of hardware and software that people and organizations use to collect, filters, process, create, and distribute data.
 - Information systems are combinations of hardware, software, and telecommunications networks that people build and use to collect, create, and distribute useful data, typically in organizational settings.'
 - Information systems are interrelated components working together to collect, process, store, and disseminate information to support decision making, coordination, control, analysis, and visualisation in an organization.
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1.3. Prerequisites of Information

Operational level management

- **The operational level is concerned with performing day to day Business transactions of the organization. Examples of users at this level of management include cashiers at a point of sale, bank tellers, nurses in a hospital, customer care staff, etc.**
- **Users at this level use make structured decisions. This means that they have defined rules that guide them while making decisions. For example, if a store sells items on credit and they have a credit policy that has some set limit on the borrowing. All the sales person needs to decide whether to give credit to a customer or not is based on the current credit information from**

Tactical level management

- This organization level is dominated by middle-level managers, heads of departments, supervisors, etc. The users at this level usually oversee the activities of the users at the operational management level.
- Tactical users make semi-structured decisions. The decisions are partly based on set guidelines and judgmental calls. As an example, a tactical manager can check the credit limit and payments history of a customer and decide to make an exception to raise the credit limit for a particular customer. The decision is partly structured in the sense that the tactical manager has to use existing information to identify a payments history that

Strategic level management

- **This is the most senior level in an organization. The users at this level make unstructured decisions. Senior level managers are concerned with the long-term planning of the organization. They use information from tactical managers and external data to guide them when making unstructured decisions.**

1.4. Need of information

technology

- **The development of Information Technology has made the education system simpler, easier, and widespread.**
- **Diffusion of e-governance on a large scale.**
- **Participation of the public in governance and policymaking. Fast economic development.**
- **Development of remote areas.**
- **Technology helps the police in nabbing the criminals.**
- **The judiciary and other administrative services can also take the help of technology to make work easier and faster.**
- **Highly beneficial for the common people, as they can access their rights and can take legal action against the person who violates his/her rights.**

COMPONENTS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

1. Computer hardware

- **This is the physical technology that works with information. Hardware can be as small as a smartphone that fits in a pocket or as large as a supercomputer that fills a building.**
- **Hardware also includes the peripheral devices that work with computers, such as keyboards, external disk drives, and routers. With the rise of the Internet of things, in which anything from home appliances to cars to clothes will be able to receive and transmit data, sensors that interact with computers are permeating the human environment.**

2. Computer software

- **The hardware needs to know what to do, and that is the role of software. The software can be divided into two types: system software and application software.**
- **The primary piece of system software is the operating system, such as Windows or iOS, which manages the hardware's operation. Application software is designed for specific tasks, such as handling a spreadsheet,**

3. Telecommunications

- **This component connects the hardware together to form a network. Connections can be through wires, such as Ethernet cables or fiber optics, or wireless, such as through Wi-Fi. A network can be designed to tie together computers in a specific area, such as an office or a school, through a local area network (LAN). If computers are more dispersed, the network is called a wide area network (WAN).**
- **The Internet itself can be considered a network of networks.**

4. Databases and data warehouses

- **This component is where the ,material' that the other components work with resides. A database is a place where data is collected and from which it can be retrieved by querying it using one or more specific criteria.**
- **A data warehouse contains all of the data in whatever form that an organization needs. Databases and data warehouses have assumed even greater importance in information systems with the emergence of ,big data,' a term for the truly**

5. Human resources and procedures

- The final, and possibly most important, component of information systems is the human element: the people that are needed to run the system and the procedures they follow so that the knowledge in the huge databases and data warehouses can be turned into learning that can interpret what has happened in the past and guide future action.**

1.6. Role of Information Technology in Business

- **The role of technology in Business caused a tremendous growth in Business and commerce. Business concepts and models were revolutionized as a result of the introduction of technology. This is because technology gave a new and better approach on how to go about with Business. It provided a faster, more convenient, and more efficient way of performing Business transactions.**
 - **Some of actions of technology in Business include accounting systems, management information systems, point of sales systems, and other simpler or more complicated tools. Even the calculator is a product of technology. It is indeed unfathomable to summon the idea of going back to the days where everything was done manually, which basically means starting all over again from scratch.**
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1.6. Role of Information

Technology in Business.....

- Technology in Business made it possible to have a wider reach in the global market.
- The basic example is the Internet, which is now a common marketing tool to attract more consumers in availing products and services offered by various Businesses.
- Information technology is all about storing, manipulating, distributing and processing information. Over the past few years, IT has replaced the conventional modes of Businesses with innovative technological tools. In addition to the increased output and efficiency, IT has introduced new concepts such as e-commerce

1.6. Role of Information Technology in Business.....

Productivity

- Technological applications, such as relational database technology, computer-aided designing, word processing, spreadsheets and other software programming, increase productivity of Businesses.
- Business corporations maximize their commercial advantage by making the right use of IT tools. For instance, Michael Dell, founder of Dell Inc., introduced the online selling concept for personal computers. Today, customers around the globe order Dell products from the comfort of their homes via the Internet

1.6. Role of Information Technology in Business.....

Monitoring

IT is used for monitoring areas of the company that are not utilizing resources efficiently. For instance, Dell made use of real-time inventory and supply monitoring to produce only that number of computer systems that were demanded by Dell customers, reducing the cost of overproduction.

Business Performance Management

According to bestpricecomputers.co.uk, BPM is defined as a management culture, which helps Businesses to optimize their performance by analyzing processes using applications like OLAP (Online Analytical Processing), and EIS (Executive Information Systems).

1.6. Role of Information

Technology in Business..... E-commerce

E-commerce is buying and selling services and goods over the Internet. Online operations reduce the time and personnel required for Business processes. It also reduces costs in areas like labour, document preparation, telephoning, and mail preparation.

Improved Organizational Communication

Important platforms such as conferencing software, email, video chat, company intranets and the internet in general. IT allows Businesses to easily hold virtual meetings with staff and clients around the world without having to spend time and money on travel. At the same time, employees can access and share information and collaborate on their work regardless of location; employees can even work remotely so

1.6. Role of Information Technology in Business.....

More Efficient Daily Operations

Another role of IT in Business is to improve the efficiency of operations so that the company can complete tasks quicker and cheaper. This often happens with the help of enterprise software and a centralized company database. Rather than having to get workers to count and monitor inventory, companies can use inventory management software that checks real - time levels, provides helpful reports to managers and can even trigger orders when the supply is low. tured enterprise resource planning software to make it easier to do accounting tasks, manage human resources, monitor the supply chain, generate invoices and make supply purchases.

1.6. Role of Information

Technology in Business.....

Better Customer Experience

IT also makes it easier to provide a good customer experience through improved customer service, easier customized marketing and e-commerce. Rather than only being able to reach the company during Business hours, customers can conveniently interact with the company on its website and through social media, email and custom instant messaging services. Through tracking customers' previous purchases with marketing software, companies can send customized promotions that better meet customers' needs and result in more likely sales. Customers also benefit from being able to purchase products and services from the company's website.

1.6. Role of Information

Technology in Business.....

Information Technology and Business Decision-Making

- The role of information technology in management decision-making is seen in tools such as ERP software and DSS that help managers see company performance data in real time so that they can make more informed decisions.
- Such software presents an online dashboard with information about the company's finances, customers, sales and marketing trends and inventory levels. Managers can use the data to decide which products to promote or stop selling, where to cut expenses, which customers need support and when to place supply and materials orders.

Other Business Roles of IT

- **Internet-enabled systems, such as secure entry systems and wireless cameras, help improve Business security and reduce risks of theft and loss of confidential information.**
- **IT allows companies to store important company data in a database in the cloud to reduce paper waste, increase security and allow for easy backups.**
- **IT allows companies to expand internationally as easily as setting up a multi-language website that markets to global customers and allows purchases in multiple currencies.**

Other Business Roles of IT...

- **Companies can use online recruitment to find more qualified job candidates and handle most of the hiring process online.**
- **From enabling telecommuting to reducing energy use through modern systems, IT has a role in company sustainability that can save money and improve the company's reputation.**
- **IT, getting the latest information about your competitors and the market is as easy as searching Google on your computer or smartphone.**

Thank
you!

